

Periodate as an Analytical Reagent—Part VI : Estimation of Hg (II) and its Application in the Indirect Determination of Glucose, Fructose, Maltose, Lactose, Furfural, Gallic Acid, Tannic Acid, Formaldehyde, Acetaldehyde and Benzaldehyde

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Mercury(II), after being reduced to elemental state, has been oxidised with sodium metaperiodate in presence of potassium bromide and boric acid and the alkali borate formed, which is a measure of mercury(II) taken, directly titrated with acid. The application of mercury(II) estimation has been made in the indirect determination of glucose, fructose, maltose, lactose, furfural, gallic acid, tannic acid, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde by reacting them with potassium mercuric iodide in alkaline medium and estimating the elemental mercury formed with metaperiodate. Accurate results have been obtained.

SODIUM metaperiodate has been used for the determination of mercury (II). It has been reduced to elemental state with formalin¹ in an alkaline medium and subsequently oxidised by metaperiodate using a crystal of iodine as the catalyst in presence of potassium bromide and boric acid. Freshly precipitated mercury is converted with sodium metaperiodate-sodium bromide solution into the complex compound sodium mercury bromide according to the equation :

The alkali borate formed in the reaction (eq. 1) has been estimated which corresponds to the amount of mercury(II) present in the solution.

The oxidation of mercury by metaperiodate has been found to be slow. A crystal of iodine has, therefore, been added to hasten the oxidation. Iodine oxidises mercury in accordance with the equation :

The iodide formed (eq. 2) reacts with metaperiodate to liberate iodine,

so that the net result is the reaction as shown by equation 1. To avoid interference of iodine with the determination of free alkali liberated in the reaction, some boric acid has been added. The alkali borate thus formed, which is a measure of the free alkali liberated, has been titrated with standard hydrochloric acid to methyl red end point.

Application of the mercury estimation has been made in the determination of glucose, fructose, maltose, lactose, furfural, gallic acid, tannic acid, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde. These substances have been treated with potassium mercuric iodide in alkaline solution^{2,3} and the mercury precipitated has been determined by metaperiodate as before.

The method is suitable for the determination of mercury (II) and is of practical value in the determination of sublimate in which mercury cannot be estimated by the Volhard method. It can also be applied to the determination of mercury in organic compounds after a conventional decomposition with persulphate and sulphuric acid. Only one standard solution is required and as such has an edge over methods, which utilise more than one standard solution^{1,4,5}.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade (BDH, analar or Merck GR), and were standardised by usual methods.

Determination of mercury (II): From an aliquot of mercury (II) solution containing 30–200 mg of Hg, the metal was reduced to elemental state with formalin in an alkaline medium¹ and filtered through gooch crucible. The washed precipitate, alongwith the filter bed, was transferred to a stoppered flask containing an excess of sodium metaperiodate (5–10 ml of 1% solution), potassium bromide (1 g), a crystal of iodine and boric acid (1 g). The reaction mixture was thoroughly shaken till the precipitate was dissolved completely and titrated with 0.1 N hydrochloric acid to methyl red end point. The titre of

the acid corresponded to the amount of mercury (II) present in the solution. The results are recorded in table 1.

TABLE I. ESTIMATION OF MERCURY(II)

Amount taken mg	Amount found mg
36.9	37.1
73.8	73.7
110.7	110.3
147.6	147.6
184.5	184.1

Determination of formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde: An aliquot, containing 40–200 mg of the substance, was taken in a stoppered flask and 50 ml of mercural solution (400 ml distilled water, 37 g KCl, 60 g HgCl₂, 160 g KI, 250 ml of 40% KOH solution) was added. The flask was set aside for one hour and the precipitated mercury was taken to a gooch crucible, washed with hot water and determined by sodium metaperiodate as before. The results are recorded in Table 2.

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TABLE 2. ESTIMATION OF GLUCOSE, FRUCTOSE, MALTOSE, LACTOSE, FURFURAL, GALLIC ACID, TANNIC ACID, FORMALDEHYDE, ACETALDEHYDE AND BENZALDEHYDE

Substance	Amount taken mg	Amount found mg	Substance	Amount taken mg	Amount found mg
Glucose	38.3	38.3	Gallic Acid	34.7	34.7
	57.5	57.4		52.1	52.1
	76.7	76.5		62.5	62.6
	95.6	95.7		69.4	69.6
	115.1	114.9		86.8	86.5
Fructose	23.8	23.8	Tannic Acid	55.8	55.8
	35.8	35.7		83.6	83.6
	47.5	47.6		111.6	111.5
	59.2	59.5		139.4	139.6
	71.3	71.5		167.4	167.3
Maltose	61.9	61.9	Formaldehyde	43.2	43.3
	92.9	92.9		51.8	51.9
	123.9	124.2		60.5	60.4
	151.8	152.2		69.1	69.1
	230.4	230.1		77.8	77.7
Lactose	34.6	34.6	Acetaldehyde	52.8	52.8
	69.1	69.1		63.4	63.3
	103.7	103.8		73.9	74.0
	137.9	138.2		79.2	79.2
	172.9	172.9		95.0	95.1
Furfural	52.2	52.2	Benzaldehyde	106.0	106.0
	62.6	62.7		132.5	132.7
	78.3	78.4		159.0	158.8
	88.7	88.8		187.5	185.5
	104.4	104.2		198.9	198.7

Determination of glucose, fructose, maltose, lactose, furfural, gallic acid and tannic acid: To a known volume of the solution, containing 20–300 mg of the substance to be determined, was added 25 ml of a solution containing 2.5 g of mercuric chloride and 8 g of potassium iodide per 100 ml followed by 50 ml of 10% sodium carbonate solution. For furfural and tannic and gallic acids, 50 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide and 50 ml of 30% sodium hydroxide were added respectively in place of sodium carbonate solution. The reaction mixture was boiled for 10 min. and cooled. The precipitated mercury was filtered off through gooch crucible, thoroughly washed with hot water and determined by metaperiodate as before. The results are given in Table 2.

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